

Effects of Online Teaching and Mental Ability Grouping on Achievement in Organic Chemistry among University Students in South-West, Nigeria,

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Abstract

This article investigated the effect of online teaching strategy (using Google online classroom) and mental ability groupings on achievement in organic chemistry among university students in southwest, Nigeria. The study was carried out among 100 level science students in two Nigeria universities in the southwest, Nigeria. Students involved were those offering basic organic chemistry as a pre-requisite course leading to the award of Bachelors' Degree in science, applied science and Science Education. The study adopted a pre-test, posttest, quasi experimental and control group research design using a 2 x 2 factorial representation. A total of 160 undergraduate students offering chemistry were involved in the study and data analysis was by Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). Result of finding affirmed the efficacy and supremacy of online teaching strategy over the conventional teacher-student classroom interaction teaching strategy ($F_{(1,155)}=49.015$, $p < 0.05$; $n^2 = .22$). It also revealed that students' mental ability had a significant effect on students' achievement in organic chemistry (mean difference = 12.71, $p < 0.05$). The study recommended that, chemistry teachers especially at the undergraduate level should adopt online teaching method in the teaching of organic chemistry. This should be done in such a manner that the gap between high and low mental ability students is bridged.

Keywords: mental ability, online teaching, undergraduates, achievement, organic chemistry.

Introduction

The bedrock of growth and development of any nation is rooted in Science and Technology. Any nation that ignores this does so at its peril. Babayemi (2014, p1) as cited in Babayemi and Ahmed (2019) stated that "Science and Technology remains the arrow head that determines the degree, direction and dimension of national development". In order to achieve national goals, the role of science teaching cannot be under estimated. In line with this, nations all over the world (including Nigeria) have emphasized the teaching of science and technology – based subjects at different levels of Education in their various countries' education systems. Arising from this, nations all over the world had made the teaching of science and technology-based subjects compulsory at the basic and higher levels of education. In line with this, Nigeria's National policy of Education 1981 revised in 2013 has emphasized and listed Chemistry as one of the core subjects to be taught at the Senior Secondary level of Nigeria Educational System.

Chemistry as a subject plays a central role in the scientific and technological advancement of any nation. This has been widely reported by researchers in the field of Science and Science Education both in Nigeria and at the international levels. These past studies include those of Raimi (2022); Raimi and Sodamade (2020).

In spite of the importance so attached to Chemistry as a school subject, evidence abound that students' performance in the subject had been on the decline. A number of reasons have been put forth as responsible for the observed downward trend in students' achievement in the subject. This varies from the use of improper teaching method by the teacher (Esparaco, 2005, Raimi, 2002; Babayemi & Utibe, 2017) to poor students' attitudes towards science especially chemistry (Raimi, 2022a; 2022b). Other factors that have been identified to be responsible for poor learning outcome in Chemistry are improper exposure to laboratory activities (Olagunju & Babayemi, 2014; Babayemi, Itighise, Umanah, Abasi & Umoh, 2023). Babayemi and Olagunju (2015) lamented that most science classes have the problems of lack of class activities and instructional resources to teach the subjects. Other reasons for students' low performance are: poor science background in Junior Secondary School (Raimi, 2002), lack of problem-solving abilities (Raimi & Sodamade, 2018), failure to read the question and understand the question before rushing to answer (WAEC, 2016, 2019), poor quantitative ability (Orji, 2000; Raimi, 2002) and students' gender (Olagunju & Babayemi, 2014; Raimi & Sodamade, 2019; Umanah & Sunday, 2022; Kopezynski & Silva 2023).

These problems have made science educators to focus on how to improve the teaching and learning of Chemistry over the years (Raimi, & Babayemi, 2013; Itighise & Babayemi, 2018; Etiubon, Akpan & Udoh, 2021). Such efforts include, problem solving approach Orji 2000, Raimi 2002, Raimi and Adesoji 2004), the use of practical oriented teaching (Raimi 1999), the use of on-line teaching method (Akpan, Itighise & Umo, 2022; Raimi, 2022).

On-line teaching and learning have come to stay in educational process all over the world due to digital and technological advancements and other recent pandemic challenges (Ebola, Covid-19, etc) that shook the entire world system. This means that the way teachers teach and the way learners learn have gone beyond offline classroom interactions to online virtual classroom interactions. Both offline and online teaching and learning, take advantages of online and offline teachers and resources for students' learning gains. The focus of this research is on online, which an additional platform for students to learn irrespective of the warranting conditions. Such warranting conditions include large traditional class size (overpopulated physical classrooms) (Babayemi, Akpan & Babalola, 2017), insufficient practical apparatus for scientific investigations, insufficient human resources including teachers and other school supportive staff, unavailability of school laboratory (Babayemi & Kareem, 2019), library and workshop places, pandemic experience limiting students from accessing schools and natural disorders, among others. Other conditions that may warrant the use of online teaching and learning, as reported by Carlen and Jobring (2005) include the potential of online learning communities to facilitate communication between people who share common interests and learn collaboratively using networked technologies. They however posited that researchers and designers have to understand the social practices in order to explore and develop technological tools for such collaboration and communication.

Many of the studies conducted on online instructional approach have been carried out at the secondary school level. There is also the need to focus attention on how to improve students' achievement in Chemistry especially at the university undergraduate level. It is also necessary especially among students who are not pursuing careers in core chemistry but take chemistry courses as pre requisites in pursuance of careers in science and technology related fields. The present study intends to fill this gap. The present study also investigated the effect of the use of on – line teaching strategy on students' achievement in basic organic chemistry. Performance of students in Chemistry can also be influenced by other learners' characteristics such as mental ability. Studies in this area have been reported in the past by researchers (Raimi & Adeoye, 1999; Yang & Ekpeyong, 2000; Raimi, 2002; Babayemi & Akinsola, 2014). Reports from these studies have expressed divergent views regarding the relationship between ability and performance in Chemistry. Some, such as Raimi and Akinyemi (1997), Adeoye and Raimi 2005, Iyang and Ekpeyong (2002) found a direct relationship between the two variables, others such as Adegoke (2000) and Kasali (2000), Adeoye and Raimi (2005), Raimi & Sodamade (2018), Babayemi and Ahmed 2019) did not establish such relationship.

In views of this divergent views, there is need to investigate further on the effect of students' mental ability on achievement in Chemistry especially basic organic chemistry. Hence, the present study investigated the relationship between the two variables at the undergraduate level especially when it involves the use on-line teaching strategy. The present study also investigated the interaction effects of students' mental ability on achievement especially when on- line teaching is employed as a means of instruction and assessment at the university level.

Objectives of the study

The study determined undergraduates' achievement in basic organic chemistry using online teaching and mental ability groupings. Specifically, the study:

1. Determine the achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using online strategy and those exposed to conventional method.

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2. Determine the mean achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using mental ability grouping strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method.
3. Determine the interaction effect between the achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using online teaching method and mental ability grouping method.

Research questions

1. Is there any significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using online teaching strategy and those taught with lecture method?
2. Is there any significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using mental ability grouping strategy and those taught with the conventional lecture method?
3. Is there any interaction effect between the achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using online teaching strategy and those taught with mental ability grouping method?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using online teaching strategy and those exposed to the conventional lecture method.
2. There is no significant difference between mean achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using mental ability grouping strategy and those exposed to the conventional lecture method.
3. There is no significant interaction effect between the mean achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using online and mental ability grouping strategies.

Methodology

The study employed a pre-test, post-test experimental control group design using a 2 x 2 factorial representation. The population for the study comprised mainly all the undergraduate students of the two universities in Oyo state, Nigeria, that participated in the study. Only undergraduate students in the two universities that have CBT centers participated in the study. The purposive sampling technique was used in selecting participant for the study. A total of 160 undergraduate students which comprised 59 males and 101 females were involved. Age range of students' sample as at the time of this investigation was 17-25 years. The students' sample are those offering basic organic chemistry as one of the basic and compulsory science courses in the universities., These students are those who have studied for two semesters at the university or undergraduate level. This is in addition to their background knowledge of organic chemistry at the secondary level which qualifies them to enroll in. their various proposed career in the universities.

Two valid, reliable and relevant instruments were used to collect relevant data for the study. The two instruments are Chemistry achievement Test (CAT) and Mental Ability Test (MAT). The CAT is a 100 – item multiple choice to which students were to provide answers. Each CAT item has for options A – D out of which one is correct. The MAT is a standard Oti – Lenon (1976) and modified by Raimi (2002) mental Ability Test. it is a standard test for categorizing learners into mental ability groups. The two instruments were subjected to further reliability test by administering them among the 100 Level students of another public university that did not take part in the main study. A test-retest reliability coefficient for the instrument was very strong. CAT (0.76) and MAT (0.75). There are two main groups in the study. These are the experimental and the control groups. In the experimental group, online teaching strategy was used to teach the content of the course, basic organic chemistry. The two teachers handling the courses in the two universities handled the instructional sessions. These teachers were subjected to 3 – week training workshop on the use of online strategy through the Google classroom. Two observers were also appointed as research assistants who monitored the implementation of the treatment procedure. Before the classroom sessions, the students were requested to acquire g – mail address while a link through which they could connect the classroom online was provided. During the online classroom interaction, students were allowed to ask questions, raised observation and passed comments. The teacher took time to attend to students' questions, comments and observations. The experiment lasted for sixteen weeks. 3 weeks of training, 12 weeks of experiment and one week for test administration.

In the control group, students were exposed to basic organic chemistry content using the conventional lecture method. Here, there existed teacher – students' interaction. Instructional session took place for the same number of weeks as in the experimental group. As in the experimental group, students were given the opportunity to ask questions, pass comments, make remarks and raise observations, while the lecturer was on hand to attend to students' requests. As the lesson progressed, students were also exposed to formative evaluation. At the end of instruction, students were given the same summative evaluation as in the experimental group. After the treatment in each group, students were subjected to post-test achievement test. Students in

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both the experimental and control groups were given the MAT to respond to. The test was administered mid-way in to the experiment. The administration was achieved through the teachers who handled the instructional sessions of the study. This was also done with the assistance of the observers (research assistants). The test was collected and scored accordingly. The result of the scoring was used to categorize the students into High and Low ability groups. The categorization was done by finding the mean ability score after pooling the ability scores for all the sample together, which gave ($\bar{x} = 49.7$). Any student who scored ≥ 49.7 in the MAT is adjudged as having high mental ability while those with MAT score <49.7 were considered as having low mental ability. By this, the sample were categorized into High and Low mental ability groups.

Data collected were subjected to descriptive analysis of means and inferential statistical Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). An estimated marginal Means for Post–Achievement was carried out in order to determine the magnitude of the difference between the experimental group and control group. Bonferroni post hoc analysis was also carried out in order to determine the direction and rational of the difference among the identified groups.

Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using online teaching strategy and those exposed to lecture method

Table 1: Summary of ANCOVA of Post – Achievement in Chemistry by Treatment and Mental Ability

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	56823.208	4	14205.802	100.560	.000	.722	
Intercept	12874.177	1	12874.177	91.134	.000	.370	
Pre-Test	29.146	1	29.146	.206	.650	.001	
Treatment	6924.220	1	6924.220	49.015	.000	.240	
Mental Ability	1563.927	1	1563.927	11.071	.001	.067	
Treatment * Mental Ability	371.963	1	371.963	2.633	.107	.017	
Error	21896.392	155	141.267				
Total	371814.000	160					
Corrected Total	78719.600	159					

Source: Raimi et al 2022

Table 1 shows that treatment had a significant main effect on students’ achievement in Chemistry ($F_{(1; 159)} = 49.015$; $p < .05$, $\eta^2 = .240$), hence, the null hypothesis one is hereby rejected. The effect size is 24%. This implies that 24% of the post – achievement of students score in Chemistry is accounted for by the treatment applied. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the post-achievement of students in chemistry. In order to determine the magnitude of the significant main effect across treatment groups, the estimated marginal means of the treatment groups was carried out and the result is as presented in Table 2:

Table 2: Estimated Marginal Means for Post achievement by Treatment

Treatment	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Experimental Group	59.761	1.535	56.729	62.792
Control Group	32.977	3.507	26.051	39.904

Source: Raimi et al 2022

Table 2 shows that the students in the experimental group had a higher adjusted post-achievement mean score (59.76) than students in the control group (32.97). This implies that the students in the experimental group outperformed their counterparts in the control group by the virtue of the treatment applied.

Table 3: Bonferroni Post-hoc Analysis of Post-Achievement by Treatment

(I) Treatment	(J) Treatment	Mean Difference (I – J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound

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Experimental Group	Control Group	26.783*	3.826	.000	19.226	34.340
Control Group	Experimental Group	-26.783*	3.826	.000	- 34.340	-19.226

Source: Raimi et al 2022

Table 3 shows that the difference between the post-achievement of students in chemistry is significant (Mean Difference = 26.78; $p < .05$). This implies that the main effect of the treatment is due to the significant difference that exists in the achievement of students in the experimental and the control group.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using mental ability grouping strategy and those exposed to lecture method.

Table 1 shows that mental ability had a significant main effect on students' achievement in chemistry ($F_{(1; 159)} = 11.07$; $p > .05$; $\eta^2 = .067$), hence, the null hypothesis two is hereby rejected. The effect size is 6.7. This implies that 6.7% of variance in students' post-achievement in Chemistry was accounted for by the treatment applied. Table 4 below shows the estimated marginal mean of this post-achievement across the two levels of mental ability.

Table 4: Estimated Marginal Means for Post-Achievement by Mental Ability

Mental Ability	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
High	52.724	3.521	45.769	59.679
Low	40.014	1.495	37.061	42.967

Source: Raimi et al 2022

Table 4 shows that the students with high mental ability had a higher adjusted post-achievement mean score (52.72) than students with low mental ability (40.1). This implies that the students with high mental ability outperformed their counterparts with low mental ability. Hence, this difference is the source of the main effect of mental ability, as shown in table 5 below:

Table 5: Bonferroni Post-hoc Analysis of Post-Achievement by Mental Ability

(I) Mental Ability	(J) Mental Ability	Mean Difference (I - J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
High	Low	12.710*	3.820	.001	5.164	20.256
Low	High	-12.710*	3.820	.001	- 20.256	-5.164

Source: Raimi et al 2022

Table 5 shows that there is a significant difference between the post achievement of students with high mental ability and students with low mental ability (Mean Difference = 12.71; $p < .05$).

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant interaction effect between the achievement scores of students taught using online and mental ability grouping strategies.

Treatment and mental ability on students' achievement in basic organic Chemistry ($F_{(1; 155)} = 2.63$; $p > .05$; $\eta^2 = .017$). Hence, the null hypothesis three is hereby accepted. This implies that the interaction of treatment and mental ability did not bring about a significant difference in the post-achievement scores of students in chemistry.

Discussion of Findings

The study further confirms that using Google classroom interaction on-line could be a better strategy to promoting good learning organic chemistry. It was found that the use of this strategy significantly enhanced science undergraduates' performance in Basic Organic Chemistry. It revealed that students in the experimental group (on-line teaching) group achieved significantly better than students who were taught via the conventional classroom interaction methods. This is why researchers Akpan, Itighise and Umo (2023) submitted that it is very necessary to integrate digital tools and platforms in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics teaching (STEM) to enhance instructional process. The result of this study is in line with an earlier and related study in (Koller & Ng, 2014, Maqsood et al, 2022 and Raimi, 2022), which affirmed the supremacy of the use of online teaching method over the conventional teaching method. The implication of this finding is that, students' achievement is enhanced through on-line teaching strategy especially when it involved learning of Basic Organic Chemistry among undergraduate students. This then means that, chemistry teachers especially at the undergraduate level should adopt its use in their teaching. The use of the method can be aided by the school authorities, school administrators and policy makers.

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This can be achieved in a number of ways. On the one hand, the school authority could plan the school curriculum, lecture timetable and other school activities to accommodate the use of this strategy in the teaching of Chemistry and science at the undergraduate level. On the other hand, adequate efforts should be made for university teachers and undergraduates to fix their programs for a successful implementation of the strategy.

Adopting this method also has the advantage of enabling chemistry teachers at the higher level of education an easy coverage of their course content especially where lecturers have to combine other administrative works such as attendance to students' problems (both personal and academic), preparation of students' results, attendance at meetings with teaching. Lecturers can reschedule their lectures to other convenient time and in collaboration with the students. Furthermore, nowadays with the lowering of JAMB cut off marks and the attendant upsurge in enrolment in the face of inadequate infrastructures, it is becoming increasingly difficult for lecturers to cope with effective learning and evaluating students. Adopting this strategy will minimize the problems associated with large classes and its attendant problems. As a result of this practicing chemistry teachers at the University level are urged to use this method of teaching due to its potency in assisting both learners and their teachers.

The use of online teaching requires more commitment from teachers in terms of commitment and dedication and self-development. In the light of this, Heads of departments, Dean of faculties, University administrators are urged to put modalities in place and provide enabling school environment that can aid the use of on-line teaching supported with materials that can aid the Chemistry and indeed science teachers' use of the method including self-development programs. Such should include organizing refresher courses and seminars, training programme, workshops that bother on improving the teaching of chemistry. This should be supported with adequate funding and provision of adequate and workable network facilities at subsidized rate for both students and lecturers. These have the potential of assisting the institution minimize wastage and to maximize the use of their facilities in the face of ever-increasing students' enrolment. The finding is however negating that of Maqsood, salif, Mazhar and Arif (2022) in their study "positive and negative effect of online teaching "when they found that online teaching is fraught with many negative features ranging from students' 'on participation in learning, to less physical interaction between students and teacher leading to students' isolation in the learning process and laziness on the part of students.

The study also revealed that there exists a significant difference between the mean achievement scores in basic organic chemistry of students taught using mental ability strategy and those exposed to conventional lecture method. The direction of significance is in favor of students with high mental ability. This finding shows that students with high mental ability performed better in Basic Organic Chemistry than their counterparts with low mental ability, especially when online teaching strategy is employed in instruction delivery. The result of this study is in line with those of Raimi (2002); Babayemi and Akinsola (2014) that confirmed significant main effect of numerical and mental abilities on achievement at different levels of educational attainment including cognitive achievement. Raimi (2002) found that the effect was more on the control group especially in comparison with different experimental groups when supplemental (problem solving) method was used as a means of instruction. The result was also in line with those of other studies such as, Hacker (1992), Raimi and Oduwaye (1997), Salawu (2001) and Babayemi (2014) when they found something similar in their different studies.

Furthermore, critical look at the result of the analysis, it was found that there exists a wide difference in the mean scores of students in the high and low ability (mean difference = 12.71 $p < 0.05$). This implies that Chemistry teachers need to employ strategies that have the potential of bridging educational gap between below average students and their counterparts with high mental ability. Such methods include online (Google Classroom) teaching and attempt should be made to create conducive learning atmosphere that is capable of achieving this.

The insignificant interaction effect of treatment and mental ability on chemistry achievement has some educational implications. This shows that, the significant main effect on post achievement scores in Basic Organic Chemistry was as a result of treatment (that is the use of online teaching) irrespective of ability. Students in the experimental group performed significantly better than their counterparts in the control group. This was affirmed by the non-significant interaction of treatment and ability as observed in table 1. The insignificant main effect based on ability perhaps might be due to the use of online teaching strategy which assisted low ability group cope with the content of the course taught. As practicing Chemistry and science teachers, enhanced teaching technique needed to be adopted to bridge the gap between students with low and high mental ability such as Online Teaching method. This also corroborates the research findings by Raimi 2002, Raimi and Adesoji 2004, who in their earlier related studies recommended the use of enhanced teaching strategy to teach Chemistry at the secondary school level.

Conclusion

In this article, the main and interaction effects of online teaching strategy and students' mental ability on achievement in Basic Organic Chemistry was investigated, at the undergraduate level. In line with general expectation, the study affirmed

that the use of online classroom interaction significantly enhanced students' performance in Basic Organic Chemistry when compared with the use of teacher–students' physical classroom interaction mode of teaching. The significant effect was found to be prominent irrespective of students' mental ability.

Recommendations

On the basis of these findings, it is recommended that,

1. Science teachers and indeed chemistry teachers at undergraduate level should employ the use of online teaching strategy, especially in the teaching of basic organic chemistry. This should be done regardless of students' mental ability. Teachers.
2. In adopting the use of online teaching strategy, a level plane and conducive learning environment should be provided for learner of different ability groupings can learn without any hindrance.
3. Furthermore, heads of departments, deans of faculties and university authorities should provide appropriate and adequate infrastructures that can enhance the use of online teaching mode of instruction. This has the potential of solving a number of educational and institutional problems relating to school administration, curriculum planning and implementation.

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